

UNDERSTANDING THE CURRENT ROLE OF ENGLISH AS A GLOBAL LANGUAGE

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Annotation: It is undeniable fact that English has been spread all over the world as a dominant global language which is widely used in all sphere: from the science to the agriculture including internet which is played a globalized role in the world. Undoubtedly, English is the key of the world's door which gives an opens opportunity to contact someone who is from the four sides of the world: the East, the West; the North and the South.

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But what is the origin of this language which has a major role in the world? If we talk about Anglosphere, where the majority of people speak English natively, they are American English, Australian, British, Canadian, Irish, New Zealand, Scottish and Welsh English which are considered as a native English.

In a word, a part of the British empire, Rwanda and Burundi, which were formerly German and then Belgian colonies; Cameroon, where only a portion of the national territory was under British mandate; and Liberia, the Philippines, the Federated States of Micronesia, the Marshall Islands, and Palau, which were all American territories, are among the exceptions.

When it comes to the Commonwealth of Nations and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations both have English as their sole official language.

According to Google, The United Nations, the European Union, NAFTA, the African Union, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the Caribbean Community, the Union of South American Nations, and many more international organizations all use English as an official language.

Nowadays, as the life is getting very fast, we can see any changes in any sphere. But it is not difficult to notice the quality of English in any field of the world. As the English language is turning to the Globish, today people try to use it in everywhere: from agriculture to the education. If we take economy, social or cultural terms, it can be easy to see how English make an impression on these spheres. As Cristopher Mc Cormick said, English is intensely learnt not only for self-improvement, but also for economic purpose.

Firstly, if people are interested in making their own business, English has been a powerful challenge for them. It is said that English contribute to the economic sector in various ways like proficiency in computers, technology and driving. Knowing English very well enables one to understand basic skills that was need in modern life. For example, employees who are good at English , can find a high salalry job around the world which effects to their family budget.

On the other hand, English is detrimental force to the world's cultural diversity. As cultures are expressed and transmitted with the learning of languages, speakers try to communicate using their mother tongue. They prefer to speak in English. This is because in most urban areas in the world's countries family communicate only using English. They believe that English is a global language and it is considered as an international one. Diving to know very well brings them to forget their values, traditions and clothing style is dramatically changed. For these reasons connection between English and culture effects badly to the culture of non-native countries. Speaking English is essential nowadays since it opens up a world of possibilities in terms of communication, quality of life and education. Because English is the most widely spoken foreign language among the world.

Additionally, with raid economic growth, the role of English has been growing in importance. Developing countries in the past have been dependent on its abundant supply of man power in labor-intensive industries and the level of English required has been quite low. Time has changed now since many countries are on the turning point of the development into the kind of economy that depends more on skill

intensive industries. At this point, a steady supply of skilled manpower and technical know how becomes a necessity. The skills of information processing, analysing, experimenting and collaborating needed are applied in English context. It is also where English as a global language becomes increasingly necessary.

Furthermore, majority people on the planet can communicate in English for a variety of purposes; for example, a multicultural meeting or a conversation with a foreigner who does not know the local language is used as a lingua.

To sum up, English has become a truly global language, because of using technologies and globalization which are changed it from English to the Globish.

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